

The Impact of Supply Chain Strategy and Supply Chain Flexibility on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME'S) In Indian Automobile Sector

Author Details: Amit Chandak

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Institute of Engineering & Science, IPS Academy
A.B. Road, Indore (India)

Abstract

In modern business environment due to rapid technological changes, innovation, policies of government companies facing tremendous challenges, specially small and medium enterprise (SMEs). The Indian SMEs try to integrate their business process strategically within their supply chain network. Despite the fact that intensive research has been done in supply chain management (SCM) a little research has been done so far in which this issue is discuss with respect to a SMEs in India. The study examines the impact of supply chain strategy and flexibility on the SMEs business performance in the Indian automobile SMSs. A quantitative research survey was conducted among 202 SMEs owners/managers. SPSS 23.0 was used to analyze the data. Structural path modeling (SEM) was conducted to assess the proposed model analysis and to test the statistically significant relationship of the hypothesis. This research is an attempt to bridges the gap and deficiency on the research done previously in this issue and particularly about the relationship between supply chain flexibility dimensions on supply chain performance. Hence, the first and foremost objective of this study is to find how supply chain strategy (SCS) and supply chain flexibility (SCF) dimensions are related with supply chain performance (SCP) dimensions. Furthermore, innovative strategy and efficient and effective supply chain flexibility is directly related to improve supply chain performance. This research is based on research done by Fantasy et al. (2009) in his research he suggested that further investigation can be made on his research in a different geographical region. To widen understanding on this topic and to go after the recommendation of the preceding research, this research closely related to Fantasy et al. (2009) and this research is done on the SMEs of Indian automotive industries which in current situation having much importance. The research study results revealed that chain strategy and flexibility positively impacted performance of supply chain and their by influence SMEs business performance

Keywords-Supply Chain Flexibility (SCF), Supply Chain Performance (SCP), Supply chain strategy(SCS)

1. INTRODUCTION

Supply chain plays a vital role in building customer value and business growth (Martinsen & Bjorklund, 2012). Supply chain is a connecting link between organizations together for building value in products/services to satisfy the customer's needs. Previous research shown that there is a definite relationship between implementation of effective and efficient supply chain management (SCM) practices like supply chain strategy supply chain flexibility (Souresh Bhattacharya, Sunil Giri et al.2014) The industry is experiencing an evolutionary phase in which automotive supply chain has a vital role to play. Due to dynamic industry environment and new competencies the Indian SMEs supply chain is expected to advance significantly because it gives a source of competitive advantage for the industry. Hence, a careful integration of supply chain strategy and supply chain flexibility with supply chain performance can improve small and medium enterprises' (SMEs) performance, create value, and generate capital into a business. In the current scenario implementation of proper supply chain management practices can improve operational efficiency and profit. This research highlighted the impact of supply chain strategy and flexible supply chain on the performance for overcoming challenges. It helps in identifying future trends in the automotive SMEs supply chains and matching contemporary SCM practices. Effective and efficient supply chain strategy and supply chain flexibility minimization of cost associated with supply chain which is the most important aspect for SMEs. The most vital aspect of this value chain is the complex system of SCM which integrated with manufacturing. These critical dimensions of SCM (Strategy, Flexibility & Performance) will help business executive to take decisions on SCM. In today's cutthroat competition and limited availability of resources the firm's must be better utilized to understand better application of SCM and thereby provide better value to customers and improve the performance of the organization (Chow et al., 2006). SMEs, therefore, are a significant division and driver of economic growth in India and as a result, government is placing emphasis on innovative SMEs research and development (Oke, Burke & Myers, 2007; Nielsen & Thomsen, 2009). The Indian SMEs facing a challenge after demonetization, therefore the purpose of the study is to determine the impact of supply chain strategy and flexibility on supply chain performance and business performance of SMEs in India.

2. THEORETICAL REVIEW, HYPOTHESIS AND RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

2.1 Supply chain strategy and SMEs performance

Supply chain strategy involve the demand uncertainty, diminishing product life cycle, manufacturing strategies, collection and mining of information about competitors, and competitive environment, with the aim of winning and maintaining competitive advantages of enterprises (Zha & Chen, 2009). Due to these uncertainties different supply chain strategies emerged (H.L.Lee, 2002). Hence, setting the accurate SC strategy is necessary for companies. Firms must needed the strategy that integrate and coordinate right through the supply chain to produce the performance of supply chain members (Cohen and Roussel, 2005; Wisner, 2003). Firms must need to adopt a strategy that suits both its product and marketplace (Mason-Jones et al. (2000) and Lewicka (2011). According to Fisher (1997) the first step in developing supply chain strategy is to understand the demand of product.

Towill and Christopher (2002) recommend that there are three types of supply chain strategies: agile supply chains; lean supply chains; and hybrid supply chains. Sufian, 2010 argued that the information technology should facilitate implementing the business strategy. For taking competitive advantages customer convenience strategies such as customized logistics and agility increase demand while operational strategies and lean network increases supply side capabilities (E. A. Morash 2001). Enhancing performance within a supply chain network requires a well-organized and planned integrated strategy so that the whole process of supplying and delivering to customers is efficient and effective (Kim, 2009; Flynn, Huo, & Zhao, 2010).

H₁: *Supply chain strategy has a significant positive influence on SMEs performance*

2.2 Supply chain flexibility and SMEs performance

In today's fast growing market the supply chain of SMEs facing tremendous challenges on a daily basis which require direct attention and quick response. Hence, a rigid or a strict idea and objectives that confine the SMEs to operate in one direction may have a negative effect on the performance. In today's competitive environment, flexibility is needed to respond to uncertainty in environment, changing customer demand and quality product at low cost, timely delivery, organizational disruptions and performance losses (Sanchez & Perez, 2005; Shang & Marlow, 2005). The supply chain flexibility is very necessary for customer's satisfaction. Flexibility is a complex and multidimensional concept (Sethi and Sethi 1990; Upton 1994, 1995; Garavelli 2003). The study, therefore, hypothesizes that:

H₂: *Supply chain flexibility has a significant positive influence on SMEs performance.*

2.3 Supply chain performance and SMEs performance

Supply chain performance is a vital and multi-faced rapidly developing area of research in supply chain management. Researchers have indicated that supply chain networks can facilitate SMEs to be more competitive and increase service performance to customers as well as improving their organizational performance (Chin, Hamid, Rasli & Baharun, 2012). The objectives of performance measurement are to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of a supply chain (Beamon 1999; Gunasekaran et al. 2001), and also consider the overall supply chain goals and the metrics to be applied (Gunasekaran et al. 2001). The organizational performance refers to how well an organization acquire its market-oriented goals, financial goals in terms of performance items such as return on assets (ROA), market share and growth rate. (Vickery et al. 1991). In supply chain performance quality, cost, response time and service level are the performance indicators (Christopher and Towill, 2001). Lippman (2001) identified the effect of product cycle time, due date performance, cost and quality on operational performance. This study, therefore, proposes that:

H₃: *Supply chain performance has a significant positive influence on SME performance.*

The proposed conceptual framework showing the hypothesized relationship between the research variables is presented in Figure 1

Figure 1: Conceptual framework showing the hypothesized causal relationships

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Sampling and data collection

There is diversity in collection of data there are different methods that can be used for collecting data viz. using a survey strategy, such as structured observation, interviews and questionnaires (Saunders et al. 2007). In statistically testing the enormous amount of structured data needed from different respondent who fill the questionnaire. Hence large number of respondents that therefore should be contacted and the small information available from respondents, the questionnaire is selected to collect the data needed to test the above hypotheses (Cooper and Schindler 2003; Saunders et al. 2007). Besides this (Cooper and Schindler 2003)

- A questionnaire allows get in touch with otherwise inaccessible contacts
- It is less expensive (it costs less time and money to reach a large sample)
- A questionnaire is perceived as more unspecified
- It allows respondents time to think about the questions
- The data can easy be worked out used for analyzing and testing

Although a questionnaire is the most common choice to collect the data needed in this thesis, it has also some disadvantages

3.2 Measuring instrument

The questionnaire was divided into three sections, namely supply chain strategy, supply chain flexibility, and supply chain performance. The research scales were adopted mainly based on previous works. Minor adaptations were made in order to fit the research context and purpose. Supply chain networks measuring items were adapted from Kenny and Fahy (2011). All the measurement items were measured on a five-point Likert scales to express the degree of agreement, with one being strongly disagree, to five being strongly agree.

4. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

4.1 Reliability Analysis

The Cronbach's alpha was conducted to assess the reliability of each scale. Cronbach Alpha values over 0.7 indicate that all the data can be considered consistent (Nunnally, 1978). This value is presented in Table 1

Table 1: Reliability of each construct

Dimensions	Cronbach's alpha (α)	No. of Items in construct
Innovative Strategy	0.863	5
Customer Oriented Strategy	0.925	5
Agile Supply Chain Strategy	0.858	7
Innovation & New product / Future Research Flexibility	0.863	7
Sourcing Flexibility & Process Flexibility	0.925	9
Existing Product Flexibility	0.858	5
Trans-shipment and Delivery Flexibility	0.915	9
Information Flexibility	0.849	5
Cost Performance	0.874	6
Logistics Performance	0.778	4
Quality Performance & Customer's Satisfaction	0.887	7

4.2 Hypotheses testing results

This section deals with the examines the Smart PLS results. The full form of PLS is Partial least squares (PLS) analysis it is an alternative method over Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression, canonical correlation, or covariance-based structural equation modeling (SEM) of systems of independent and response variables. PLS is sometimes called "composite-based SEM", "component-based SEM", or "variance-based SEM", in contrast to "covariance-based SEM," which is the usual type (e.g., implemented by Stata, SAS, MPlus, LISREL, Amos EQS and other software packages used in statically analysis). It was hypothesized that there is a positive relationship between the research construct measuring supply chain strategy, flexibility, supply chain performance and SMEs performance. Table 2 shows the causal paths and hypotheses. The t-values are all above 1.96 indicating statistical significant at the level of 5 percent (Lei & Wu, 2007). Further, the model showed that the entire hypothesis is accepted at 5% significant level as shown in table 2.

Table 2: Results of structural equation model analysis

Causal Path	Hypothesis	Path Coefficients	t-value	Significance Level
SCS <--- SMEP	H ₁ (+)	0.479	3.857	Accepted at p<0.05
SCF <--- SMEP	H ₂ (+)	0.579	7.856	Accepted at p<0.05
SCP <--- SMEP	H ₃ (+)	0.356	9.874	Accepted at p<0.05

Path significance: * $p < 0.05$

(t-value > 1.96 (for 2-tailed) which is equivalent to $p < 0.05$).

SCS (Supply Chain Strategy), SCF (Supply Chain Flexibility), SMEP (Small & Medium Enterprise Performance)

Figure 2 show the smart- PLS2.0 result in which three construct of supply chain strategy ,5 construct of supply chain flexibility and three construct of supply chain performance are include. The participating SMEs answer the question based on these construct .The supply chain strategy and supply chain flexibility taken as independent variable and supply chain performance as dependent variable.

Figure 2 Research Model tested using Smart PLS 2.0

5. DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The first hypothesis (**H₁**) supply chain strategy has a significantly positive influence on SMEs performance. This hypothesis was supported with a direct effect (path coefficient = 0.479, t-value = 3.857, p < 0.05). The majority of the participating SMEs in this study believe that supply chain strategy can enhance their competitive capability to survive through efficient use of business resources and effective implementation of innovative ideas. The majority of the SMEs also indicate that customer oriented strategy serves as an opportunity to gain competitive advantage for their product. The agile supply chain strategy involves formulating and implementing integrated logistics-related strategies in order to manage product delivery effectively to customers within the organization as well as across the supply chain.

The second hypothesis (**H₂**) posited that supply chain flexibility has a significantly positive influence on SMEs supply chain integration. The hypothesis is supported (path coefficient = 0.579, t-value = 7.856, p < 0.05). The majority of the participating SMEs agreed that the flexibility is important in supply chain network. This indicates that those SMEs who are able to implement supply chain flexibility in their supply chain they can compete better and respond faster than their rivals. To efficiently managing the supply chain, organizations need to adopt proper supply chain strategies & flexibility into supply management chain practices (Sufian, 2010). Effective & efficient supply chain management is vital determinant to building and sustaining competitive advantage in the market place.

The third hypothesis (**H₃**) posited that supply chain performance has a significantly positive influence on SMEs performance. The hypothesis is supported (path coefficient = 0.356, t-value = 9.874, p < 0.05). The majority of the participating SMEs agreed that supply chain performance requires integrated information systems that connect all members within the supply chain for it to improve cost-efficiency, profit, customer satisfaction, and superior return on investment.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The research findings show that the current supply chain system of SMEs may be less effective if not strategically incorporated to improve performance. This suggests that SMEs existing supply chain should be developed through a strategic involvement which strengthen relationship between customers and suppliers. Innovative and customer oriented strategy can play a strategic role in boosting SMEs supply chain performance and also promote SMEs collaborative relationship with larger organizations. This will lead to cost reduction in operation costs and risk, improve SMEs product quality, enhance smooth product and service flow and improved SMEs business strategy techniques

7. LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

There are a number of limitations that influence the generalizability of this study.

(i) This study limited only on SMEs operates in automobile sector. One of the limitations of this single-sector study is that the conclusions may not be generalizable to other sectors. Future studies replicating this research across various industries and sector would enhance the understanding of supply chain performance.

(ii) The sample choice was based on a convenience sample, which is often used for exploratory work (Zikmund, 2003), rather than a random probability sample. Further research could be conducted using a random probability sample.

(iii) The sample represented a limited number of companies in one sector only.

(iv) The study is based on a questionnaire. Therefore, there is a possibility of respondents answering questions in a way that is perceived to be more desirable or acceptable than what is actually experienced or believed.

8. CONCLUSION

For SMEs to compete successfully within the competitor environment, they need to understand and implement the right business strategies. This study revealed that positive significant relationships exist between supply chain strategy, supply chain flexibility, supply chain performance and SMEs performance, which further confirm the proposed research conceptual framework for SMEs business performance. This study also suggests to both SMEs owners and government or policy makers in India importance of supply chain network relationship for SMEs business performance and economic growth. The research model, however, provides some insights and directions for SMEs supply chain performance researchers.

REFERENCES

- i. Albino, V., Dangelico, R.M. & Pontrandolfo, P. (2012). "Do inter-organizational collaboration enhances a firm's environmental performance? A study of largest U.S. companies". *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol. 37, pp. 304-315.
- ii. Angappa Gunasekarana (2008) et al "Responsive Supply Chain: A Competitive Strategy in a Networked Economy" *International Journal of Management Science*, Omega 36, 549 – 564.
- iii. Arawati Agus (2011) "Supply Chain Management, Supply Chain Flexibility and Business Performance" *Journal of Global Strategic Management* | 09 | 2011, June.
- iv. Anant Deshpande, "Supply Chain Management Dimensions, Supply Chain Performance and Organizational Performance: An Integrated Framework" *International Journal of Business and Management* Vol.7, No.8.
- v. Benita M. Beamon (1999) "Measuring supply chain performance" *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 19 No. 3, 1999, pp. 275-292, # MCB University Press, 0144-3577.
- vi. Benita M. Beamon, (1998) "Supply Chain Design and Analysis: Models and Methods" *International Journal of Production Economics* Vol. 55, No. 3, pp. 281-294.
- vii. Braunscheidel, M.J. & Suresh, N.C. (2009). "The organisational antecedents of a firm's supply chain agility for risk mitigation and response". *Journal of Operations Management*, Vol. 27, pp. 119-140.
- viii. Chin, T.A., Hamid, A.B.A., Rasli, A. & Baharun, R. (2012). "Adoption of supply chain management in SMEs". *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Vol. 65, pp. 614-619.
- ix. Droge, C., VickerY, S. & Jacobs, M.A. (2012). "Does supply chain integration mediate the relationships between product/process strategy and service performance? An empirical study". *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol. 137, pp.250-262.
- x. Flynn, B.B., Huo, B. & Zhao, X. (2010). "The impact of supply chain integration on performance: a contingency and configuration approach". *Journal of Operations Management*, Vol.28, pp.58-71.
- xi. Hau L. Lee, Jason Amaral (2002), "Continuous and Sustainable Improvement through Supply Chain Performance Management" *SGSCMF-W1-2002 Supply Chain Performance Management*

- xii. Ila Manuj, John T. Mentzer(2012) “Global supply chain risk management strategies” *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management* Vol. 38 No. 3, 2008 pp. 192-223. April 2012.
- xiii. Ilkka Sillanpaa (2011) et al “Supply Chain Performance Measurement Framework for manufacturing industries – a Theoretical Approach” *Proceedings of the 12th Management International Conference Portorož, Slovenia, 23–26 November 2011*
- xiv. Kenny, B & Fahy, J. (2011). “SMEs networking capability and international performance. In Baxter, R. & Woodside, A.G., ed. *Inter-firm networks: theory, strategy and behaviour*”. Bingley, UK: Emerald Group Publishing, pp.199-376.
- xv. Lei, P.W. & Wu, Q. (2007). “Introduction to structural equation modeling: issues and practical considerations”. *Educational Measurement*, Vol. 26, No.3, pp.33-43.
- xvi. Lei, P.W. & Wu, Q. (2007). “Introduction to structural equation modeling: issues and practical considerations”. *Educational Measurement*, Vol. 26, No.3, pp.33-43.
- xvii. Merschmann, U. & Thonemann, U.W. (2011). “Supply chain flexibility, uncertainty and firm performance: an empirical analysis of German manufacturing firms”. *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol.130, pp.43-53
- xviii. Nyoman Pujawan (2004) “A Conceptual Framework for Assessing Supply Chain Flexibility” *International Journal Integrated Supply Management*, Vol.1, No.1, 2004.
- xix. Oke, A., Burke, G. & Myers, A. (2007). “Innovation types and performance in growing UK SMEs”. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 27, No.7, pp. 735-753.
- xx. Sanchez, A.M. & Perez, M.P. (2005). “Supply chain flexibility and firm performance: A conceptual model and empirical study in the automotive industry”. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 25, 7, pp. 681-700
- xxi. Simona Danielo Grigore, “Supply Chain Flexibility” *Romanian Economic and Business Review –Vol. 2 No.1.*
- xxii. Thakkar, J., Kanda, A. & Deshmukh, S.G. (2008). “Supply chain management in SMEs: development of constructs and propositions”. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing & Logistics*, Vol. 20, 1. pp. 97-131.
- xxiii. Vinzi, V.E., Chin, W.W., Henseler, J. & Wang, H. (2010). “Handbook of partial least squares: concepts, methods and application”. Heidelberg, Germany: Springer-Verlag.
- xxiv. Wu, I.L., Chuang, C. H. & Hsu, C.H. (2014). “Information sharing and collaborative behaviors in enabling supply chain performance: a social exchange perspective”. *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol. 148, pp. 122-132.